

WAYS OF ORGANIZING INTERDISCIPLINARY COMMUNICATION OF PUPILS' IN THE PROCESS OF FORMING SINGING SKILLS

¹Ibraimov Kholboy Ibragimovich, ²Karimov Sakhob Bakhromovich

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozhi. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor.

²Teacher of Department of Music Education. Jizzakh state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395218>

Abstract. *In this article, it is mentioned that music lessons are more important than art lessons in terms of their artistry, interest, and instilling more creative pleasure, emotional feelings and figurative experiences in students. In addition, the results and conclusions obtained by applying the method of comparative comparison of music lessons with the teaching of other subjects are also presented. Also in the article, intensive growth occurs in students of the 5-7th grade, at this age, that is, at the age of 13-15, an important biological change, that is, a state of mutation occurs, and how a music teacher should act in such cases. it is stated that it is necessary.*

Keywords: *interdisciplinary communication, music, music lessons, students, educational system, artistic aesthetics, listening to music, spoon, students, classes, secondary schools, singing spoon, performing musical-rhythmic movements, music creativity, music literacy, ability, mutation, voice.*

Children at this age begin to transition from childhood to adulthood, and therefore consider this period as a transitional period. They are now starting to act like adults and want to be addressed as adults. At the same time, there are cases where they overestimate their mental and physical capabilities. Especially in the 6th grade, children finally become happy and want to express their opinion on everything, most of them are responsive and generous. Sometimes teachers have a hard time managing 6-7 graders. They don't like to be overly demanding and put them in order, and on the contrary, giving them free will also upset them.

One of the important aspects is that they start to think independently and look at everything with a critical eye.

Intensive growth occurs in 5-7 grade students. They begin to mature quickly psycho-physiologically. They grow taller, their bones begin to grow, and they develop better mentally. They are now showing signs of puberty. They try to do what they say. If they don't say it, they will quickly become angry.

It is important that at this age, that is, at the age of 13-15, an important biological change, that is, a state of mutation, occurs. The state of mutation directly depends on the vocal apparatus of the students, the vocal cords are sharply stretched and disappear. This condition is especially noticeable in boys. As a result of the dramatic lengthening and thinning of the vocal folds of boys, they now develop a new, husky, masculine voice. During the 6-7th grade, they have two types of voices.

First of all, sometimes the thin voice of their childhood prevails, and sometimes the newly formed masculine voice prevails. Such voice changes prevent them from finding their voice and singing.

A music teacher should allow them to find their exact voice, knowing in advance that such a situation will happen.

Some experts say that 6-7 graders should not be taught songs. But most practicing teachers say that it is necessary to help children of this age to get used to a new voice and to develop their singing skills in a new voice.

Taking into account the changes that occur in children, laryngology doctors work in every school. They check and monitor the changes in the throat.

The music teacher will be able to consult with the laryngologist and give permission for the student not to sing sometimes. It is necessary not to sing, especially when there is a sharp change in the voice, when there are elements of tension and redness in the throat.

In boys, the vocal cords lengthen and thicken in a short period of time. This causes an octave drop in their voice.

Before the mutation, children's voices sang in the range from the lower octave "si" (H) to the second octave "re-mi-fa" (D,E,F), but due to the mutation, they now sing from the high octave "la, si" (A,H) to the first octave "re-mi-fa" (D,E,F). they sing in the interval up to the notes.

When a new voice is formed, it is necessary to prevent tension in children's voices. Because the vocal cords and tendons are not yet well formed, they are delicate and fragile. It will be necessary to shout loudly at them, to protect them from eating hot and cold food one after the other, and to regularly warn them about this.

Usually, children of this age shout at the top of their voices to call each other, shout out their emotions and sing louder than everyone else when they sing.

13-15-year-old girls also have the mutation. But there are no signs of cracking in their voices. The vocal cords and vocal folds do not grow as fast as boys. Only 10-15 percent will grow and the vocal cords will thicken. Due to this, the change in their voice is almost imperceptible. Only in their voices can you feel the majesty of adults.

Regardless of how subtle the changes, it is recommended to do special work on preserving their sound. Sometimes you can feel their temperature rise. In such cases, it is necessary to be content with freeing them to sing and watching others carefully.

It is necessary to rely on the advice of a laryngologist to find out how the changes that occur due to puberty are taking place. Sometimes laryngologists have the right to give instructions about the need to release them from singing.

The mental development of 5-7th graders also begins to be noticeable. They will now be able to help the teacher to observe freedom in the classroom, take care of the flowers and establish order in the classroom during the lesson.

In the process of systematically singing as a team, they feel how well the teacher's requirements are being met. They will learn the structure of intervals and chords, as well as different scales, given according to music theory. They can talk about composers in detail. They can learn the idea of musical works, and give the characteristics of sound character by looking at their timbres.

Pupils of this age can understand different actions well. They are also able to perform various actions on how to position themselves on the stage.

To students, taking into account these possibilities $\frac{2}{3}$; $\frac{3}{4}$; $\frac{4}{4}$ it is also possible to delegate the task of conducting works. They now feel the responsibility to behave in front of students as conductors.

All students express their desire to conduct the class choir. The teacher should try to find a way to satisfy their wishes.

The process of listening to music allows students to form their imaginations. As a result of getting used to listening to the content of the music, they try to imagine the reality of the work through their own imagination. In such cases, the teacher should be able to allow each student to think freely and create conditions for independent thinking. In this way, they are taught from concrete thinking to abstract thinking. They get used to perceiving abstract things instead of drawing conclusions based on concrete facts.

Adolescent children's attitude to work changes a lot. They put their heart into every job and try to do it well. Music is a field that is perceived mainly through mental work, and they now reach the level where they can make their own thoughts from the ideological content of musical works. They absorb a number of norms related to moral education. Especially through songs about work, they get information about the work of people who are engaged in other specialties. In particular, they will learn about the work of farmers, the profession of hairdressers, drivers and other professions. In particular, his love for the teaching profession is increasing.

Students sing samples of songs about mothers and sisters on the occasion of March 8. Through these songs, it is possible to deeply feel the need to treat women with respect and dignity. In grades 5-7, students gain a deeper understanding of the concepts of Motherland, Motherland, and Motherland.

In the lessons about the motherland, they will learn about the beauty of the Uzbek land, fertile lands, garden meadows, velvety dirt filled with red tulips, muddy rivers, and fruits. They also develop aesthetic thinking. Especially when they sing about beauty, they realize that their voices should be beautiful and pleasant enough to express this beauty.

Thus, it is important to study the psychological condition of students at the teenage age, to learn about the physiological and biological changes that occur in them, and to form their singing skills.

REFERENCES

1. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –Т., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
2. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
3. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
4. Karimov S. “The importance of using interdisciplinary integration in shaping students knowledge and skills”. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). India 2021-yil. 8-avgust. 264-268 bet.
5. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
6. Атауллаев Ф. Ф. У., Ибраимов Х. И. Понятие профессионально-коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей в психолого-педагогических исследованиях //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 1 (42). – С. 70-74.
7. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.

8. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
9. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).